

18. Uluslararası Eğitim Camiası Sempozyumu Tam Metinleri

كتاب المتون الكاملة المؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للمجتمع التربوي

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ÖN SÖZ

18. Uluslararası Eğitim Camiası Sempozyumu, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşti. Bu sempozyum, Saybilder Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Sempozyuma 5 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye hariç 8 farklı ülkeden (Birleşik Krallık, Cezayir, Fas, Irak, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Umman) katılan bilim insanlarına ait sözlü bildiri sempozyum programına dâhil edilmiştir. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltilerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir.

Başvuru süreci sonucunda 27'si Türk bilim insanları tarafından ve 37'si farklı ülkelerden katılan bilim insanları tarafından hazırlanmış toplam 64 bildiri sözlü sunuma uygun bulunmuştur. Bu kitapta bilim insanlarının sempozyumda sunduğu bildirilerin tam metinlerine yer verilmiştir. Bu sunumların geniş kitlelere ulaşarak alana faydalı olmasını ve yeni çalışmalara ilham vermesini diliyorum.

Sempozyumun bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Doç. Dr. Sami Baskın
Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

مقدمة

نحن سعداء بتقديم هذا الكتاب الذى يجمع بين دفتيه الأبحاث العلمية الكاملة التى تم تقديمها خلال فعاليات المؤتمر الدولى الثامن عشر للمجتمع التربوى، والذى انعقد فى أنقرة فى الفترة ما بين 8 و11 أكتوبر. كان المؤتمر منصة متميزة جمعت بين نخبة من الأكاديميين والباحثين فى مجال التربية من أكثر من عشر دول، حيث أسهمت هذه اللقاءات العلمية فى تبادل المعرفة والخبرات حول أحدث المستجدات فى مجال التعليم وتطوير المناهج.

تميز المؤتمر بالتنوع الأكاديمى الذى عكس غنى الطروحات التى تناولت قضايا تربوية متعددة، بدءاً من التعليم المدرسى والجامعى إلى مناهج التعليم المتخصصة والتربية الخاصة. كما ناقش المؤتمر التحديات الراهنة التى تواجه النظم التعليمية فى العالم، فى ظل التحولات الرقمية والعولمة، فضلاً عن تقديم نماذج ابتكارية لتعزيز التعليم القائم على التكنولوجيا وتطوير المهارات القيادية لدى الطلاب والمعلمين.

هذا الكتاب هو نتاج جهد جماعى من الباحثين الذين أسهموا فى تعزيز الفهم العميق للقضايا التربوية، وقدموا رؤى نقدية تهدف إلى تحسين العملية التعليمية على المستويين المحلى والدولى. يضم هذا العمل دراسات متنوعة شملت مجالات البحث الكمى والنوعى، مع تسليط الضوء على أهمية التعليم الشامل ودوره فى بناء مجتمعات مستدامة وقادرة على مواجهة تحديات المستقبل.

نأمل أن يكون هذا الكتاب إضافة قيمة للمكتبة التربوية، وأن يسهم فى إثراء الحوار الأكاديمى حول سبل تطوير التعليم، وأن يستفيد منه الباحثون وصناع القرار فى تحسين جودة التعليم بما يحقق التقدم المطلوب فى هذا المجال الحيوى.

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**"Innovation With Digital Technology" Module and Artificial Intelligence Applications in
The Training of French Language Teachers in France**

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Özet

Fransa'nın Besançon şehrinde, Université de Franche-Comté'nin bir birimi olan Centre de Linguistique Appliquée'de (Uygulamalı Dil Merkezi) (CLA) gerçekleştirilen iki haftalık (5-16.08.2024) öğretmen eğitiminde dünyanın farklı yerlerinden gelen birçok öğretmene iki farklı ana modül gösterilmiş ve birini seçmeleri istenmiştir. Söz konusu Uygulamalı Dil Merkezi tarafından 2024 yazında düzenlenen pedagojik eğitim, Fransızca Öğretmenlerinin uzmanlık alanlarını zenginleştirmelerini ve dil sınıfı için somut ve yenilikçi uygulamaları deneyimlemelerini sağlamıştır. Katılan öğretmenler, yeni pedagojik yaklaşımlar keşfetme, mesleki pratiklerini geliştirme ve dünyanın dört bir yanından gelen öğretmenlerle deneyimlerini paylaşma fırsatı bulmuşlardır. Bu eğitim kapsamında 30 saatlik modül olan "Innover avec le numérique" ve 10 saatlik olan serbest modül "Motiver les adolescents" ve 10 saatlik çeşitli forum etkinlikleri deneyimlenmiştir. Bahsedilen 30 saatlik eğitim boyunca üç farklı eğitim verilmiştir: "Mobiliser les outils du numérique en classe de FLE", "Intégrer l'IA dans l'apprentissage du français" ve "Introduire le jeu dans ses enseignements". Belirtilen eğitimlerde çeşitli yapay zeka uygulamaları yapılmış, sınıf içi etkinlik olarak çok farklı internet üzerinden online oynanabilecek dil oyunları deneyimlenmiştir. Fransızca öğretmenleri bu eğitim boyunca Dijital oyun ve etkinliklerin temelleri; sınıfta metin ve ses kullanımı, sabit ve hareketli görüntü kullanımı konularında bilgilendirilmiştir. Sınıf uygulamalarının çeşitlendirilmesi, cep telefonu ile ilgili teknolojiler ve dijital araçları kullanarak ders içi faaliyetler ve mini projeler oluşturma konuları tartışılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Öğretmen eğitimi, Fransızca öğretimi/öğrenimi, dijital technology, yapay zeka.

**"Innovation With Digital Technology" Module and Artificial Intelligence Applications in
The Training of French Language Teachers in France**

Abstract

During the two-week teacher training program (August 5-16, 2024) held at the Centre de Linguistique Appliquée (CLA), a unit of the Université de Franche-Comté in Besançon, France, teachers from various parts of the world were presented with two main modules and asked to select one. This pedagogical training, organized by the CLA during the summer, allowed French language teachers to enrich their areas of expertise and experiment with concrete and innovative practices for the language classroom. The participating teachers had the opportunity to explore new pedagogical approaches, enhance their professional practices, and

share their experiences with educators worldwide. As part of the program, they experienced a 30-hour module titled "Innover avec le numérique" and a 10-hour optional module "Motiver les adolescents", along with 10 hours of various forum activities. During the 30-hour training, three different workshops were offered: "Mobiliser les outils du numérique en classe de FLE" (Using Digital Tools in the French as a Foreign Language Classroom), "Intégrer l'IA dans l'apprentissage du français" (Integrating AI into French Language Learning), and "Introduire le jeu dans ses enseignements" (Incorporating Games into Teaching). The specified training sessions included various applications of artificial intelligence, and participants experienced a wide range of online language games that could be played in the classroom as activities. Throughout the program, French language teachers were informed about the fundamentals of digital games and activities, including the use of text, sound, and both static and dynamic images in the classroom. Discussions also covered diversifying classroom practices, utilizing mobile phone technologies, and incorporating digital tools to create classroom activities and mini-projects.

Keywords: Teacher Training, French Language Teaching/Learning, Digital Technology, Artificial Intelligence.

Introduction

During the two-week teacher training program (August 5-16, 2024) held at the "Centre de Linguistique Appliquée (CLA)", a unit of the Franche-Comté University in Besançon, France, teachers from various parts of the world were presented with two main modules and asked to select one. The first module is titled "Enrichir ses pratiques de classe" (Enriching Classroom Practices) and the second module is titled "Innover avec le numérique" (Innovating with Digital Tools).

As part of the program, teachers experienced a 30-hour module titled "Innover avec le numérique" and a 10-hour optional module "Motiver les adolescents", along with 10 hours of various forum activities. During the 30-hour training, three different workshops were offered: "Mobiliser les outils du numérique en classe de FLE" (Using Digital Tools in the French as a Foreign Language Classroom), "Intégrer l'IA dans l'apprentissage du français" (Integrating AI into French Language Learning), and "Introduire le jeu dans ses enseignements" (Incorporating Games into Teaching). The specified training sessions included multiple applications of artificial intelligence, and participants experienced a wide range of online language games that could be played in the classroom as activities. Throughout the program, French language teachers were informed about the fundamentals of digital games and activities, including the use of text, sound, and static and dynamic images in the classroom. Nowadays, foreign language teachers are expected to be familiar with digital games and Web 2.0 tools and integrate them into their classrooms. In this context, classroom activities presented as games can be created by incorporating colorful, dynamic visuals into applications like Kahoot, Plickers, Wooclap, and Quizlet. Questions can be added to these websites in various areas such as vocabulary and grammar, and videos or audio recordings in the foreign language can also be used. On the Vocaroo website, the teacher can record his/her voice and later include this recording in an activity created on Kahoot or Plickers. Additionally, a sound library website called "La sonothèque" offers numerous ready-made sound recordings that can be downloaded for free by anyone. For example, a few nature sounds (forest, bird, or wave sounds) can be added from this website, allowing for a speaking activity in the foreign

language with students at the beginning of the lesson. Students can be encouraged to speak in a foreign language by asking questions such as "What do you hear?" or "In what kind of environment do you think this sound was made?". Another activity that can be conducted in the classroom is creating an "Escape Game" using websites like Genially. An Escape Game involves trying to "escape" from a specific area, such as a classroom, within a set time by following given instructions and solving mysterious clues. In this game, students are immersed in a specific historical setting and scenario, where they are expected to solve certain enigmas. Through this process, students learn to collaborate and work together. When they encounter difficulties while following the clues provided in the game, they solve problems by communicating with one another in the target foreign language. In this way, tasks that one student may struggle with are completed by another, allowing the group to complement and support each other's abilities. Even students who tend to work more individually in the classroom will find themselves socializing through this game, leading to the development of their speaking and writing skills in the foreign language. As students enjoy playing the escape game, they may be more motivated, and their anxiety levels, often associated with learning, will decrease. In this way, the Escape Game provides an opportunity to enhance all four language skills—speaking, writing, reading, and listening—within a single activity, as it encourages students to use these skills simultaneously.

Classroom games can also be conducted with students by listening to songs in a foreign language. The website Lyricstraining can be used to learn or improve various foreign languages. For example, by selecting Slimane's song "Mon amour," which represented France in the Eurovision Song Contest, and choosing a language level in French (beginner, intermediate, advanced, or expert) on the Lyricstraining website, students can access the song's music video. As the song plays, the student is expected to fill in the blanks; the song automatically pauses at each blank, and once the student writes the correct answer, the song continues. In this way, the student enhances both their listening and writing skills in the foreign language. As shown in the image below, the number of blanks the student was unable to complete, along with their score, is displayed at the top:

In addition to all these digital tools, the content shared by foreign language teachers on social media, particularly on Instagram, can be utilized by teachers as classroom activities. Moreover, students can watch Netflix series and movies dubbed in the foreign language they wish to learn, further enhancing their language learning experience. Additionally, by adding the Language Reactor extension to Google Chrome, students can watch YouTube videos with subtitles in two languages simultaneously (for example, both English and Turkish).

Foreign language activities can also be conducted in the classroom using mobile applications. With apps like ChatterPix, Talkr, and Revive, students can take a photo of themselves and add a song, or they can upload a picture of an animal and make it "talk." Through these interactive and entertaining games, students' attention is effectively drawn to the lesson, making the learning experience more engaging.

Whether teachers want it or not, various Artificial Intelligence (AI) websites are becoming integral to foreign language education. AI language models like ChatGPT, Gemini, Perplexity, and DeepL allow students to engage in conversations, translate between languages, and assist students in various grammar topics, much like a teacher would. Some foreign language teachers ask AI for suggestions on classroom activities related to the topics they plan to teach. This illustrates that AI is becoming a companion not only for students but also for teachers. However, there are concerns among teachers about students having AI-complete their assignments instead of doing the work themselves. This issue is to be addressed as plagiarism detection programs, such as Turnitin, evolve to detect AI-generated content as well.

At the same time, it is essential to be aware of the "dangers" of the digital environment and the harmful effects of screens on young people and to manage these risks effectively. Therefore, younger learners need to engage in various digital activities under the supervision of their teachers.

Today, the diversification of classroom practices, the use of mobile technologies, and the integration of digital tools for creating in-class activities and mini-projects are being discussed in foreign language teaching. The pedagogical training organized by the Applied Language Center in Besançon, France, during the summer of 2024, allowed French teachers to enrich their areas of expertise and experience concrete and innovative practices for language classrooms. Teachers participating in this training had the chance to explore new pedagogical approaches, enhance their professional practices, and share their experiences with educators worldwide.

Keywords: Teacher Training, French Language Teaching/Learning, Digital Technology, Artificial Intelligence (AI).

References

Notes taken during the classes throughout the training in Besançon, France (August, 2024).

<https://kahoot.com/>

<https://www.plickers.com/>

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